

Speciation of ternary complexes of cobalt(II) and nickel(II) with L-glutamine and succinic acid in urea-water mixtures

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Abstract : A pH-metric investigation has been made on the speciation of Co^{II} and Ni^{II} complexes of glutamine (Gln) and succinic acid (Suc) in varying concentrations (0–36.83%, w/v) of urea-water mixtures at an ionic strength of 0.16 mol dm⁻³ and temperature 303 K. Various models for the species of these complexes are refined by using the computer programs SCPHD and MINIQUAD75. The active forms of the ligands are LH₂ and LH⁻ for succinic acid and XH₂⁺ and XH for L-glutamine. The predominant species detected for Co^{II} complexes are MLX, MLXH and MLXH₂ and for Ni^{II} are MLX and ML₂XH. The trend in the variation of stability constants of the complexes with dielectric constant is explained on the basis of electrostatic and non-electrostatic forces. The species distribution with pH at different solvent composition and the plausible equilibria for the formation of the species are also presented.

Keywords : Complex equilibria, speciation, L-glutamine, cobalt(II), nickel(II).

Protonation and complexation equilibria of Gln (L-glutamine) and Suc (succinic acid) in urea-water, ethylene glycol-water and acetonitrile-water media have been studied in this laboratory to thoroughly understand speciation of their complexes¹. The protonation constants of Glu and Suc are correlated with the dielectric constant of the medium using various solvents including dimethylformamide (DMF). Similarly, the stability constants of Ca^{II} and Mg^{II} complexes of Gln and Suc were determined in ethylene glycol-water and in acetonitrile-water mixtures^{1,2}. The speciation studies of ternary complexes of Gln and Suc with Co^{II} and Ni^{II} in urea-water mixtures have been reported in this paper.

Results and discussion

L-Glutamine (XH₂⁺) has three functional groups (amino, carboxyl and amido) but only amino and carboxyl groups can associate with protons. Succinic acid (LH₂) has two carboxyl groups and both are protonated. The present study is confined to pH range 2.5–8.0. Alkalimetric titration curves in urea-water mixtures revealed that the acido-basic equilibria of L-glutamine and succinic acid are active in the pH ranges 1.5–9.0 and 2.5–7.0, respectively¹. Based on the active forms of the ligands in this pH range, models containing various numbers and combination of complex species of Co^{II} and Ni^{II} with Gln and Suc are generated using an expert system package CEES³. These models are inputted

to the computer program, MINIQUAD75⁴ along with the alkalimetric titration data. The best-fit model is selected using the statistical parameters of the least squares residuals. The finally refined model for Co^{II} complexes contains MLX, MLXH and MLXH₂ species and that for Ni^{II} complexes contains MLX and ML₂XH species. In these complexes succinic acid acts as primary ligand (L) and glutamine acts as secondary ligand (X). The final models are given in Table 1, along with the statistical parameters.

The linear variation (Fig. 1) of stability constants of Gln and Suc complexes of Co^{II} and Ni^{II} in urea-water mixtures with 1/D (where D is dielectric constant of the medium) indicates that electrostatic forces are dominating the equilibrium process under the present experimental conditions. Urea acts as a denaturant of macromolecules by interacting with peptide groups through its amido group and by breaking the water structure⁵. Hence, the stability of the species decreases with increasing urea content. Another reason for the decreased stability of the ternary complexes is the ligation power of urea.

Stability of ternary complexes : The formation of mononuclear, unprotonated binary and ternary complexes from a mixture of metal ion (M) and primary (L) and secondary (X) ligands can be shown as the equilibria given in eq. (1).

Table 1. Best-fit chemical models of Co^{II} and Ni^{II} complexes of L-glutamine and succinic acid in urea-water mixtures

No. of titrations in each percentage = 6, temp. = 303 K, ionic strength = 0.16 mol dm⁻³

% w/v	log β _{MLX} (SD)			NP	U _{corr} × 10 ⁶	χ ²	Skew- ness	Kurto- sis	R-factor
	1110	1111	1112						
Co ^{II} complexes (pH range : 2.5–8.0)									
5.80	8.41(1)	15.87(1)	20.74(2)	140	1.43	155.31	0.04	5.86	0.012
11.52	7.61(6)	14.10(1)	18.06(6)	147	2.29	120.30	1.37	9.19	0.015
20.31	7.17(5)	13.43(6)	17.20(8)	123	1.33	98.22	1.12	5.87	0.016
29.64	6.82(5)	12.72(1)	15.45(3)	87	1.25	30.21	-0.24	3.72	0.017
36.83	6.32(8)	10.96(9)	13.80(5)	110	1.30	98.33	1.01	4.47	0.013
Ni ^{II} complexes (pH range : 2.5–8.0)									
	1110	1211							
5.80	7.61(6)	15.19(2)		134	6.01	203.58	0.70	3.03	0.024
11.52	7.13(2)	15.40(1)		136	4.28	54.30	0.38	2.70	0.021
20.31	6.88(1)	14.73(1)		132	1.12	61.97	0.15	3.93	0.012
29.64	6.67(1)	14.25(2)		109	6.14	54.90	1.49	10.04	0.037
36.83	6.16(8)	13.46(2)		132	1.33	192.48	0.47	3.88	0.013

The change in stability of ternary complexes as compared to their binary analogues was quantified earlier⁶. In one of the approaches the difference in stability (Δ log K) for the two reactions ML with X and M(aq) with X is compared with that calculated purely on statistical grounds. Eq. (2) can be formulated based on the properties of the cyclic systems reported⁷ earlier, from which it is clear that both the ligands in the ternary complex influence mutually to the same extent.

$$\begin{aligned}
 \Delta \log K &= \log K_{MLX}^{ML} - \log K_{MX}^M = \log K_{MLX}^{MX} - \log K_{ML}^M \\
 &= \log K_{MLX}^M - K_{ML}^M - K_{MX}^M \quad (2)
 \end{aligned}$$

Both electrostatic theory of binary complex formation and statistical arguments clearly indicate that, in the case of a given multivalent hydrated metal ion, more coordination positions will be available for the first ligand than for a second one. Hence, the order of stability $K_{ML}^M > K_{ML_2}^{ML}$ holds good. This leads to a natural expectation for Δ log K to be negative, although several exceptions^{6,8} have been found. The statistical values of Δ log K for bidentate L and X are -0.4 and -0.6 for octahedral and square planar complexes, respectively, whereas for distorted octahedral complexes the values vary between -0.9 and -0.3. Negative values of Δ log K can be understood as the secondary ligand forms a more stable complex with hydrated metal ion than with ML, which does not mean that the ternary complex is absent.

Whenever the experimental value of Δ log K exceeds the statistical value, it can be inferred that the ternary complex is formed as a result of interaction of ML with X or MX with L. Sigel postulated⁹ that Δ log K values of ternary complexes containing bipyridyl as the primary ligand were positive for O-donors (malonic acid, pyrocatechol etc.), negative for N-donors (ethylene diamine) and intermediate or many a time small negative values for amino acids with both N and O coordination sites. However, a very high negative value (-2.3) for Cu(en)(iminodiacetic acid) and a positive value (0.82) in the case of Cu(ophen)-(6,7-dihydroxy naphthalene 2-sulfonate) were also observed⁶.

Table 2. Calculation of Δ log K values from overall stability constants

$K_{ML_2XH}^M = \beta_{1111}$		$K_{ML_2XH}^M = \beta_{1211}$
$K_{MLXH_2}^M = \beta_{11/12}$		$K_{MLX}^M = \beta_{1110}$
$\Delta \log K_{1110}$	≠	$\log \beta_{1110} - \log \beta_{1100} - \log \beta_{1010}$
$\Delta \log K_{1111}$	=	$\log \beta_{1111} - \log \beta_{1101} - \log \beta_{1010}$
	=	$\log \beta_{1111} - \log \beta_{1100} - \log \beta_{1011}$
$\Delta \log K_{1112}$	=	$\log \beta_{1112} - \log \beta_{1102} - \log \beta_{1010}$
	=	$\log \beta_{1112} - \log \beta_{1100} - \log \beta_{1012}$
	=	$\log \beta_{1112} - \log \beta_{1101} - \log \beta_{1011}$
$\Delta \log K_{1211}$	=	$\log \beta_{1211} - \log \beta_{1201} - \log \beta_{1010}$
	=	$\log \beta_{1211} - \log \beta_{1200} - \log \beta_{1011}$

The formulae for the calculation of Δ log K values are given in Table 2. The Δ log K values calculated from binary and ternary complexes are incorporated in Table 3. Co^{II} and Ni^{II} ions form octahedral complexes with L-glutamine and succinic acid. For most of the systems given in Table 3 the

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tilled water. A 99.5% pure urea (E. Merck) was used without further purification. To assess the errors that might have crept into the determination of the concentration, the data were subjected to ANOVA. The strength of alkali was determined using the Gran plot method¹². The titrations were carried out in the medium containing varying concentrations (0.0–36.83%, w/v) of urea in water maintaining an ionic strength of 0.16 mol dm⁻³ with NaCl at 303.0 ± 0.1 K using a Systronics 335 pH meter. The glass electrode was equilibrated in urea-water mixture containing inert electrolyte. The correction factor (log *F*), to correct the pH meter dial reading, was determined using SCPHD program¹³. Titrations with different ratios (1 : 2 : 2, 1 : 2 : 4 and 1 : 4 : 2) of metal-to-primary ligand-to-second ligand were carried out with 0.4 mol dm⁻³ sodium hydroxide. Other experimental details are given elsewhere¹⁴.

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